

Deliverable D2.1 – Report

Technical Specification of the SXT-100

Grant Agreement number: **101017116**

Project acronym: **CoCID**

Project title: **Compact Cell Imaging Device**

Call: **H2020-ICT-2020-2**

Type of action: **RIA**

Project start: **01.01.2021 (duration 48 months)**

A Nano-CT for Biological Cell Imaging

SiriusXT has developed a high throughput, bench-top, Soft X-Ray Microscope which produces high resolution 3D images of the internal structure of biological cells.

The benefits of soft x-ray tomography in imaging the sub-cellular architecture and organization of eukaryotic cells have been recognized for close to twenty years. The naturally high-contrast 3D images produced from whole, fully hydrated cells, without the need to use contrast-enhancing agents, have been instrumental in increasing disease researchers' understanding of cell structure and behaviour and have led to new insights and discoveries in cell biology.

Imaging eukaryotic cells, of approx. ten microns in diameter, with high brightness and with high throughput requires an x-ray source with a small, highly dense photon beam and with small angular divergence.

The SiriusXT SXT100 Soft X-ray Microscope is the first commercial solution that offers researchers the opportunity to image cells in their own laboratory, at a quality and performance comparable to the synchrotrons. The solution is available as both a product and a service.

The SXT-100 product.

Cryo-prepared HUH 7.5 Cells

Healthy hepatic cell

HCV-infected hepatic cell

Note *: reference library of soft x-ray imaged cell organelle, published by Alba Synchrotron

SXT-100™ Product Specification

Feature	Performance
SXM	
Operating wavelength	2.73 nm (455 eV)
Polarisation state	Unpolarised
Image field of view	~ 20 µm (at ~900X magnification)
Magnification	Adjustable (depends on objective lens)
Zone plate objective ¹	dr=35 nm (matching condenser NA = 0.039)
Image resolution (3D)	~35 nm (half pitch)
Image acquisition time	<3 hours (per 100 2D projections)
Detector	Back-illuminated X-ray CCD, 2kx2k pixels, 13.5 µm pixels, 16 bit
Raw data format	*.fits
In-line fluorescence microscope	
Configuration	Epi-fluorescence @90° to X-ray axis
Objective ²	User specified, long work distance
Channels	4-channels: Hoechst, GFP, RFP, Alexa Fluor 647
Sample presentation	
Sample tilt range	+60° to -60°
Sample support ³	Standard 3mm carbon coated TEM grid
Sample type ⁴	Typ. adherent cells, 3 µm to 8 µm thick
Sample state ⁵	Typ. vitrified by plunge freezing
Laboratory requirements	
System dimensions	3 m x 2 m x 1 m (L x W x H)
Power	10 kW
Cooling water	<16°C @ 20 L/min
Lab temperature	21 +/- 1 °C
Lab humidity	< 50%
Gas supply	Ar or N2 (N6.0 Certified)

¹Partial coherence can be obtained with the use of a different objective NA.

²Objective is on a xz stage and can be retracted away from the cold sample when not in use. Typically we have used 10X and 50X objectives for grid screening, but higher magnification shorter working distance objectives can also be accommodated.

³Other support types can be accommodated for correlative work, such as FEI autogrids and cryo-FIB lift-out grids.

⁴Non adherent cells have also been prepared and imaged on TEM grids with the SXT-100.

⁵Samples are typically vitrified, but critical point dried and chemically fixed samples have also been imaged with high contrast on the SXT-100.